

Supplementary Fig. S1. Representative immunohistochemistry images.

Supplementary Fig. S1. Representative immunohistochemistry images. Representative immunohistochemistry (IHC) images of HER2 (A), CB₂R (B) and EGFR expression (C) in samples from the TMAs from Hospitals 12 de Octubre and Puerta de Hierro, with staining intensities indicated in arbitrary units. Scale bar, 100 μ m (A) and (B) and 250 μ m (C).